

Analysis of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Civil Servant Performance Through Public Innovation in Pamekasan Regency Government

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the influence of transformational leadership and organizational culture on employee performance through product innovation. The sample in this study was 198 employees. The analysis technique used SEM. The results of the analysis show that transformational leadership and organizational culture influence employee performance. Leaders who are able to inspire, motivate, and create a positive work atmosphere, as well as an organizational culture that supports collaborative, innovative, and accountable values have been proven to improve employee performance. Transformational leadership and organizational culture influence public innovation. Public innovation influences employee performance. Innovation developed in public organizations can accelerate work processes and increase efficiency, but also provide space for employees to be creative and improve service quality, thus directly impacting employee performance. Transformational leadership and organizational culture have a very important role in improving employee performance, but the influence of both becomes more effective when mediated by public innovation. Public innovation then plays a role as a key driver in changing work systems, accelerating services, and increasing bureaucratic efficiency. In the Pamekasan Regency Government, the synergy between transformational leadership, positive organizational culture, and public innovation is a key strategy in developing high-performing, professional, and responsive employees to community needs.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Job performance is one of the most important variables in industrial management and organizational behavior. This concept is defined as individual behavior that provides value to the organization and contributes to the achievement of shared goals. According to Griffith & Harris (2020), work performance is not only the end result, but also a process that involves various behaviors that support organizational goals (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015). In this context, understanding and measuring work performance becomes very important for organizational success.

Employee performance greatly influences the achievement of organizational goals. Mangkunegara & Huddin (2016) explains that successful human resource management is a key to organizational survival and development. This demonstrates that good management aligns perceptions

between employees and managers, ultimately impacting the achievement of company goals. With strong employee performance, an organization will more easily achieve its goals.

Organizational culture also plays an important role in creating a productive work environment. Al Suwaidi & Rahman (2019) noted that although there are various views regarding the definition and scope of organizational culture, in general, organizational culture can be defined as an intellectual framework consisting of attitudes, values, norms, and behavioral expectations. A strong culture within a public organization can encourage employees to innovate and contribute more to achieving organizational goals. Two main approaches to understanding organizational culture are the process approach and the classification approach.

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In the context of innovation, the implementation of innovation in the public sector can improve the quality of public services (Damanpour & Schneider, 2009) and service performance (Walker, 2004). To achieve effectiveness and efficiency, the government relies heavily on the success of innovations that utilize existing resources and technology (Mulgan & Albury, 2003).

This study explores the relationship between transformational leadership, organizational culture, and civil servant performance in the Pamekasan Regency Government through public innovation. In an era characterized by rapid and complex change, a deep understanding of the relationship between these three elements is crucial. This study aims not only to provide academic insights but also to provide practical recommendations for developing better public policies by examining existing research findings.

Over the past few decades, the meaning of performance has undergone significant change. From a traditional focus on fixed jobs, there is now a broader understanding of performance in the context of dynamic organizations. The highly competitive work environment demands that organizations be responsive to change. This creates the need for a more comprehensive definition of performance, encompassing in-role performance, adaptive performance, proactive performance, and citizenship behavior.

Individual performance today encompasses multiple dimensions that are critical to organizational success. By delving deeper into new conceptualizations of performance, we can develop an integrative performance model that classifies three levels at which in-role behavior can contribute to effectiveness: individual, team, and organizational. Three distinct forms of behavior—competence, adaptability, and proactivity—need to be considered as subdimensions of work-role performance. Without strong individual performance, there can be no team performance, no organizational performance, or no overall economic performance (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015; Motowidlo et al., 2014). This suggests that managing individual performance is not only crucial for the development of the individual but also significantly impacts collective performance and the achievement of overall organizational goals (Daniels & Daniels, 2014).

Beyond individual performance, innovation is also a key factor in improving organizational performance. Marín-Idárraga and Cuartas-Marín (2019) point out that although theories exist explaining the relationship between innovation and performance, there are still many gaps that need to be filled. This study aims to verify how the relationship between innovation and performance is influenced by precursor variables such as competitive intensity and organizational slack. The results provide an important contribution to the strategic management literature by

demonstrating that organizations that encourage innovation can significantly improve performance.

When organizational performance begins to decline, a leader is needed who can take concrete steps to improve it. In a healthy organizational climate, leaders need to adopt a transformational leadership style to encourage innovation. According to Bass (2000), the characteristics of transformational leadership include intellectual stimulation, idealized influence, inspirational motivation, and individual attention. These characteristics are crucial in creating an environment that supports innovation and high performance. Innovation is key to gaining competitive advantage. Innovation strategy is crucial. This study considers the importance of performance and innovation as mediating variables in the relationship between business strategy and competitive advantage (Farida & Setiawan, 2022). The results provide evidence that successful innovation can significantly improve organizational performance. Innovation, on the other hand, can be divided into two types: radical and incremental. Radical innovation creates radically different solutions, while incremental innovation involves small improvements to existing practices.

Innovation has been shown to be a key driver in improving organizational performance. An organization's ability to innovate significantly impacts product quality and operational performance. While innovation does not always directly impact financial performance, its impact on operational performance is significant (Marín-Idárraga & Cuartas-Marín, 2019). Innovation is key to improving an organization's competitiveness and overall performance by creating new solutions that meet market needs. In the context of public services, innovation can include improvements in bureaucratic processes, the development of service applications, and improvements in the quality of interactions with the public (Damanpour & Schneider, 2009). Efforts to implement innovation not only contribute to operational efficiency but also increase public satisfaction with public services. Thus, organizations capable of innovating will have a greater competitive advantage in an increasingly complex market.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND DEVELOPMENT HYPOTHESES

Transformational leadership has a significant impact on the performance of State Civil Apparatus (ASN). Transformational leaders are able to inspire and motivate employees through a clear vision and emotional support, creating a positive work environment. When employees feel motivated and engaged, they tend to perform better (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Research shows that effective leadership encourages employee engagement and increased commitment, both of which contribute to higher performance (Podsakoff et al., 1996). In the ASN context, leaders who are able to create an inclusive and supportive

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work environment will produce employees who are more productive and committed to organizational goals. Organizational culture has a significant impact on the performance of State Civil Apparatus (ASN). A positive and supportive culture can create a conducive work environment, where employees feel valued and motivated to contribute optimally. Organizations with a strong culture, which prioritizes the values of collaboration, innovation, and accountability, tend to produce more productive and committed employees (Denison, 1990). Research shows that an organizational culture that supports individual and team development contributes to improved overall performance (Schein, 2010). In the context of civil servants (ASN), a culture that prioritizes transparency and open communication will encourage employees to work more effectively and efficiently in achieving public service goals. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H1: Transformational leadership and organizational culture have a significant influence on ASN performance

Transformational leadership is considered a key factor in driving innovation, particularly in the public sector. Transformational leaders are able to inspire and motivate employees through a clear vision and effective communication, creating an environment conducive to creativity and experimentation (Bass & Riggio, 2006). By creating a safe atmosphere for sharing ideas, these leaders encourage employees to innovate and find new solutions to public service challenges. Previous research has shown that organizations with transformational leaders are more likely to have higher levels of innovation (Jung et al., 2003). Through emotional support and recognition of employee contributions, transformational leaders can increase employee engagement and morale, which contribute to the development of innovation. Organizational culture plays a crucial role in fostering innovation, particularly in the public sector. A culture that supports collaboration, open communication, and employee engagement tends to create an environment conducive to the development of new ideas (Schein, 2010). When employees feel valued and encouraged to share knowledge, they are more likely to engage in innovative processes that improve organizational performance. Studies show that a strong organizational culture, which emphasizes the values of innovation and courage, has a positive impact on an organization's ability to innovate and adapt to change (Denison, 1990). In the context of public services, a culture that encourages creativity and experimentation can produce more effective solutions to meet community needs. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H2: Transformational leadership and organizational culture have a significant influence on public innovation.

Public innovation has a significant impact on the performance of State Civil Apparatus (ASN). The implementation of new ideas in public services can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of ASN work. Successful innovation not only improves work processes but also increases employee and public satisfaction (De Vries et al., 2016). When ASN engage in innovation, they tend to feel more motivated and committed to their duties, which in turn has a positive impact on overall performance (Jung et al., 2003). Research shows that organizations that adopt innovation in public services tend to have higher levels of performance, due to their ability to adapt to the evolving needs of society. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H3: Public innovation has a significant effect on ASN performance.

Transformational leadership is believed to have a significant influence on the performance of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) through public innovation. Transformational leaders are able to inspire and motivate employees to innovate, creating an environment that supports creativity and experimentation (Bass & Riggio, 2006). In the public sector context, effective leaders can encourage ASN to develop and implement new ideas that improve service efficiency. Successful public innovation not only increases employee satisfaction but also contributes to better performance (De Vries et al., 2016). When ASN are involved in the innovation process, they feel more involved and committed, which has a positive impact on overall performance. Organizational culture plays a significant role in influencing the performance of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) through public innovation. A culture that supports collaboration, creativity, and open communication creates an environment conducive to the development of new ideas (Schein, 2010). When employees feel valued and encouraged to innovate, they are more likely to contribute to improving organizational performance. Public innovation resulting from a strong organizational culture can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of services provided by ASN (Denison, 1990). In the public sector context, innovation not only improves work processes but also increases employee and public satisfaction. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

H4: Transformational leadership and organizational culture have a significant influence on ASN performance through public innovation.

III. METHOD

Operational Definition of Variables

Transformational Leadership: Transformational leadership is measured through the attitudes and behaviors of leaders who are able to inspire, motivate, and facilitate employees in achieving organizational goals. Indicators used include: the leader's ability to communicate a vision, provide emotional support, encourage innovation, and create a positive work environment. Indicators in the Transformational Leadership variable are: Idealized influence, Motivational inspiration, Intellectual stimulation, Individualized consideration.

Organizational Culture: Organizational culture is measured based on the values, norms, and practices that apply within the organization that influence employee behavior. Indicators used include: the level of collaboration between employees, open communication, innovation, and support for individual development. The organizational culture indicators in this study are: Engagement, Consistency, Adaptability, and Mission.

Public Innovation: Public innovation is measured through the application of new ideas in the processes and services provided by public organizations. Indicators used include: frequency of innovation implementation, type of innovation implemented (product, process, or service), and the impact of innovation on the efficiency and effectiveness of public services. The public innovation indicators in this study are based on Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Number 3 of 2023 (Juklak-KIPP), namely: Having novelty, Effectiveness, Benefit, Easy to Distribute, and Sustainability.

Civil Servant Performance: Civil servant performance is measured based on the achievement of assigned duties and responsibilities, as well as their contribution to organizational goals. Indicators used include: efficiency (the ability to complete tasks within the specified time), effectiveness (the ability to achieve desired results), and employee job satisfaction. The indicators in this variable are based on Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Number 6 of 2022, namely: Quantity, Quality, Time or Speed of Work Completion, and Cost.

Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2017), a population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and conclusions drawn. In this study, all 6,555 civil servants in Pamekasan Regency were included.

According to Sugiyono (2017), a sample is a part of the population and characteristics possessed by the population that is the source of research data. In this study, the sample determination uses the Slovin Formula, which is defined by Sugiyono (2019) is a formula used to obtain a sample size that is considered capable of describing the entire existing

population. In taking this sample size, the desired error or mistake is 7% (0.007), so that the sample size is 198 people.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. According to (Ghozali, 2014), SEM is an evolution of multiple equation models developed from econometric principles and combined with regulatory principles from psychology and sociology. SEM has emerged as an integral part of academic managerial research. The number of observations is very important to be able to use this method, so determining the number of samples is fundamental in this method. SEM is a set of statistical techniques that allow testing a series of relatively complex relationships that cannot be resolved by linear regression equations. SEM can also be considered as a combination of regression analysis and factor analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The model fit test, known as the Goodness of Fit Model test in SEM analysis, is conducted by assessing a number of model fit indicators, such as the Chi-Square value, probability, degrees of freedom (df), Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and Root Mean Square Residual (RMR). The following are the results of the model estimation along with the results of the Goodness of Fit Model test obtained:

Figure 1. Results of the Goodness of Fit Test of the Structural Model

Referring to the structural model estimation results shown in Figure 1, it can be concluded that the SEM model has met the Goodness of Fit Model criteria. The following is a summary of the SEM Goodness of Fit Model test results estimated in this study:

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Table1. Goodness of fit Model

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Model Results	Information
Chi-Square (df = 220)	130,256	214,986	Fit
Chi-Square Probability	≥0.05	0.064	Fit
CMIN/DF	≤2.00	1,152	Fit
RMSEA	≤0.08	0.075	Fit
AGFI	≥0.90	0.901	Fit
GFI	≥0.90	0.908	Fit
TLI	≥0.95	0.951	Fit
CFI	≥0.95	0.953	Fit

Source: Processed primary data (2025).

Based on the evaluation results of the model fit criteria (Goodness of Fit Indices) in Table 1, it can be concluded that the overall model meets the established standards. Therefore, the model developed in this study is acceptable. These results indicate that the model fits the existing data and can be used to explain the relationships between the variables identified in the study.

Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis testing in this study uses the probability value (p) as a reference. If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, it indicates a significant effect of one variable on another. A p-value of less than 0.05 indicates that the test results are statistically significant, thus the hypothesis can be accepted.

Table 2. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Variable	Direct Effect	p-value	Indirect Effect	Total Effect	Result
H1	Transformational Leadership → Public Innovation	0.204	0.012	-	-	H1 Accepted
	Organizational Culture → Public Innovation	0.235	0.024	-	-	
H2	Transformational Leadership → Employee Performance	0.387	0.000	-	-	H2 Accepted
	Organizational Culture → Employee Performance	0.544	0.000	-	-	
H3	Public Innovation → Employee Performance	0.548	0.000	-	-	H3 Accepted
H4	Transformational Leadership → Public Innovation → Employee Performance	0.204	-	0.387 x 0.548 = 0.212	0.416	H4 Accepted
	Organizational Culture → Public Innovation → Employee Performance	0.235	-	0.544 x 0.548 = 0.298	0.533	
	Transformational Leadership → Employee Performance					
	Organizational Culture → Employee Performance					

Source: Processed primary data, 2025.

DISCUSSION

1) The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance
Transformational leadership and organizational culture influence employee performance in the Pamekasan Regency Government, meaning that both factors play a strategic role in determining the level of productivity and effectiveness of civil servants within the regional government. Transformational leadership implemented by structural officials can create a positive impact through the leadership's ability to inspire, motivate, and develop employee potential to achieve the organization's established vision and mission. Transformational leaders not only act as superiors but also as mentors and role models who encourage innovation, creativity, and provide individual attention to each employee, thus creating a conducive work environment that supports performance improvement.

Transformational leadership is a leadership style that motivates employees to exceed expectations through a clear and inspiring vision. In the civil service (ASN) work environment, transformational leaders play a crucial role in fostering a productive collective work spirit. This type of leader focuses not only on achieving targets but also on the emotional and personal motivational aspects of employees. Leaders are able to serve as role models and build trusting relationships with their subordinates. With this approach, employee performance tends to improve significantly. Transformational leadership also facilitates the development of employee potential through intellectual challenges and individual empowerment. Leaders provide space for employees to innovate, express ideas, and take an active role in decision-making. This fosters a sense of responsibility and ownership for their work. When employees feel valued and empowered, they demonstrate more optimal

performance. A participatory work environment creates a collaborative atmosphere that fosters productivity.

Leaders who can motivate and inspire employees will build a strong commitment to organizational goals. In the context of civil servants (ASN), commitment to public service is strongly influenced by leadership quality. A clear vision and consistent direction from superiors provide employees with a focused work direction. Furthermore, emotional support from leaders helps employees stay motivated in facing work challenges. Transformational leaders are catalysts for high performance within organizations. Research findings support Lai et al. (2020), Qalati et al. (2022) dan Curado & Santos (2022) which explain that transformational leadership influences performance.

A strong and positive organizational culture also significantly contributes to employee performance in the Pamekasan Regency Government. The values, norms, and customs embedded within government organizations shape employees' mindsets and behaviors in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. An organizational culture that supports transparency, accountability, collaboration, and human resource development will create a work climate that encourages employees to deliver their best performance. When organizational culture aligns with transformational leadership, a strong synergy is formed to improve the quality of public services and achieve organizational performance targets.

Organizational culture is a set of values, beliefs, and norms that shape individual behavior in the workplace. A strong and positive culture is crucial in shaping consistent and professional employee work patterns. In public bureaucracies, organizational culture can strengthen service orientation, integrity, and teamwork. When organizational values serve as shared guidelines, work processes run more efficiently and effectively. This culture fosters loyal and responsible employees. Parker & Bradley (2000) stated that organizational culture can contribute significantly to improving organizational performance. A culture that is adaptive and open to change encourages employees to think creatively and innovatively. Furthermore, Robbins & Judge (2022) emphasized that organizational culture is a system of shared meaning that distinguishes one organization from another. In the context of civil servants (ASN), an organizational culture that emphasizes transparency and accountability strengthens public trust. Employees are encouraged to maintain integrity in carrying out their duties. In a complex bureaucracy like the State Civil Service (ASN), leadership quality and organizational culture determine the smooth operation and success of public services. Organizations that pay attention to these aspects will be able to create high-performing, results-oriented employees. Therefore, investing in leadership and organizational culture is a crucial strategy in bureaucratic reform. This research supports the findings of Farida &

Setiawan (2022), Piwoswar-Sulej et al. (2024), and Zhu et al. (2024), which show that a strong organizational culture can improve performance. When organizational culture is consistently built and implemented comprehensively, harmony is created between individuals and institutional goals. Employees feel a vital part of the process of achieving organizational targets, which drives continuous performance improvement.

2) The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture on Public Innovation

Transformational leadership influences public innovation, meaning that leaders with a transformational style have the ability to inspire and motivate employees to develop innovative solutions to improve the quality of public services. Transformational leadership encourages a paradigm shift in public organizations from a conventional approach to one that is more adaptive and responsive to community needs. Transformational leaders not only focus on achieving routine targets but also develop a vision of the future that encourages employees to think creatively and innovatively. This aligns with the demands of bureaucratic modernization, which requires new breakthroughs in governance and public service delivery. The results of this study support Nusair et al. (2012) and Al-Husseini & Elbeltagi, (2016) explain that transformational leadership influences public innovation.

The positive impact of transformational leadership on public innovation can also be seen in the increased cross-sector collaboration in the implementation of service programs. Leaders who are able to build partnership networks, both with the community and the private sector, will more easily mobilize resources to support various innovative initiatives. This creates synergy that strengthens the capabilities of local governments in providing services that are fast, targeted, and based on the real needs of the community. Therefore, transformational leadership is not just an ideal leadership style, but a necessity in modern governance, including in Pamekasan Regency. Rapid environmental changes, increasingly complex service challenges, and ever-increasing public expectations demand the presence of leaders who are able to embrace change and guide organizations with vision. Transformational leadership has proven to be a strong foundation for fostering public innovation that is sustainable, efficient, and has a direct impact on public welfare.

Organizational culture influences public innovation, meaning that the values, norms, and work habits embedded within an organization can encourage the creation of new ideas that benefit public services. Organizational culture is the foundation of values and norms that shape individual behavior within an institution, including the government sector. When organizational culture supports openness to new ideas, it will strengthen the drive for innovation in

public services. Public innovation is not only determined by formal structures but is also strongly influenced by the cultural aspects that exist within the organization. A culture that emphasizes values such as collaboration, risk-taking, and trust in employees will create an ecosystem conducive to innovation. Therefore, the stronger the organizational culture that supports innovation, the greater the opportunity for public innovation. The results of this study support this. Ryu (2022) and Almeida et al. (2025) explain that organizational culture influences public innovation.

In public organizations, innovation often arises from the adaptive abilities of employees in responding to dynamic societal demands. A flexible organizational culture that supports organizational learning will encourage the creation of creative, applicable solutions. Molenveld et al. (2021) emphasize that government organizations with strong organizational culture support will have a high level of responsiveness to customer needs. A responsive and open organizational culture will accelerate the innovation process that directly benefits the public. In this context, organizational culture is a key driver in transforming public services to be more effective.

A positive organizational culture also fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility among employees. When cultural values encourage participation and autonomy, employees feel more confident in developing and implementing new ideas. Innovation processes are accelerated and sustained when employees feel safe to experiment without fear of failure. This type of culture creates a psychologically safe space for innovation within the organization. This is why cultural aspects are often the difference between innovative and stagnant organizations.

Schraeder et al. (2005) agree that organizational culture is holistic, soft, difficult to change, historically based, and socially constructed. This indicates that cultural change requires a careful but consistent approach. However, if an organizational culture is rooted in the values of innovation, it will become a tremendous internal force. This culture will continue to transmit the spirit of renewal from one generation of employees to the next. In the long term, this innovative culture will shape the organization's image as an adaptive and visionary public servant.

Besides serving as a foundation for values, organizational culture also plays a guiding role in decision-making and policy formulation. Employees are more likely to make decisions that align with the adopted organizational culture. When innovation becomes part of shared values, the courage to create innovation is more appreciated and cultivated. In this situation, leaders act not only as policymakers but also as agents of cultural change. This type of work environment provides emotional and structural support for sustainable innovation.

Leadership involvement in building a culture that supports innovation is a key factor in the successful implementation

of public innovation. A strong organizational culture creates clarity of direction and a shared understanding among members regarding the importance of innovation. Initiatives to create new services or improve existing procedures will receive full support if they align with a shared work culture. In the long term, public organizations with an innovative culture will be more adaptable to changes in the external environment. This is crucial given the dynamics of society and the ever-evolving public needs.

An organizational culture that facilitates innovation is also characterized by open communication and a reward system that supports innovation. When employees feel their contributions are valued, they are more motivated to contribute new ideas. This work environment accelerates the collective process of identifying problems and finding appropriate solutions. The innovation process is no longer solely an individual responsibility but becomes embedded in the collective culture of the organization. This strengthens employee engagement in achieving the organization's strategic goals.

Organizational culture is a crucial element that drives systematic and sustainable public innovation. Historically and socially shaped culture, as Schraeder et al. (2005) explains, serves as an internal driver in addressing external challenges for public organizations. When organizational culture aligns with an innovative vision, all elements of the organization will move toward achieving shared goals. Public organizations that successfully cultivate innovation will have a competitive advantage in providing the best possible service to the public. Therefore, investing in strengthening organizational culture must be a priority in bureaucratic reform and improving public services.

3) The Influence of Public Innovation on Employee Performance

Public innovation impacts employee performance, meaning it plays a crucial role in improving employee performance, particularly in the context of government organizations, which are required to be more adaptive and responsive. Public innovation enables the simplification of work procedures, the utilization of information technology, and new approaches to public service. When innovation is implemented, employees are encouraged to adapt and improve their work quality to align with these changes. This creates a more efficient, transparent, and results-oriented work dynamic. Therefore, public innovation directly drives improved employee performance.

According to Mulgan & Albury (2003), "public innovation is about finding new ways to deliver better services, deliver more effective policies, and enhance citizen engagement in governance processes." This means that public innovation is not only about improving systems but also involving active public participation in governance. With broader public involvement, employees are required to be more adaptive,

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communicative, and responsive to community needs. This creates positive pressure that encourages employees to increase their capacity and accountability. Employee performance also improves due to greater control and expectations from the public.

The application of innovation in bureaucracy creates a more modern and measurable work system, which has a direct impact on employee performance. Information technology, for example, is used to expedite service processes and facilitate access to data needed by employees for decision-making. Utami (2023) state that "public innovation in Indonesia aims to improve the quality of public services through the use of information technology." This use of technology requires employees to improve their digital literacy and other technical skills. The greater the employee's competence in operating innovation-based systems, the greater the efficiency and effectiveness of their work.

Public innovation also creates a shift in work culture within organizations. The old, bureaucratic and slow-moving culture is gradually being replaced by one that is more dynamic and open to change. Employees are encouraged to be more proactive, collaborative, and solution-oriented in carrying out their duties. In this work climate, employees tend to demonstrate higher performance because they feel they have room to develop and contribute significantly. Thus, innovation creates a new work spirit that positively impacts performance.

Employee performance in public organizations is highly dependent on the effectiveness of work systems and the quality of the tools used. Public innovation improves both aspects by introducing information systems, streamlined service procedures, and a leaner and more responsive organizational structure. This creates time efficiencies, cost savings, and increases employee output. When employees work within a supportive and streamlined system, employee productivity significantly increases. This is clear evidence that public innovation directly impacts employee performance.

Public innovation can provide greater space for collaboration between sectors and work units. When innovation is implemented, cooperation is essential to ensure successful implementation. This collaboration opens up space for the transfer of knowledge and best practices, which will enrich employee capacity. A collaborative work environment encourages better communication and more effective role allocation. Ultimately, collaboration fostered by innovation will enhance synergy within the organization and positively impact performance. The results of this study support this. Sudibjo & Prameswari (2021) which explains that public innovation has an impact on employee performance.

4) The Influence of Transformational Leadership, Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Public Innovation

Transformational Leadership Influences Employee Performance through Public Innovation, meaning that inspiring and visionary transformational leadership can encourage the creation of various breakthroughs in public services, which ultimately improves overall employee performance. Transformational leaders not only direct, but also guide and provide space for employees to innovate in completing work and providing the best service to the public. The work environment created by transformational leaders usually supports the exploration of new ideas and the application of relevant technology for work efficiency. When public innovation is strategically organized and supported by leaders, employees feel empowered and encouraged to create new, more effective ways of completing tasks. Therefore, public innovation becomes a mediator that influences transformational leadership to improve employee performance.

Transformational leaders possess characteristics that stimulate their subordinates' intellectual capacity to think creatively and deviate from conventional work practices. Leaders encourage and trust employees to take calculated risks to improve services. This fosters an innovative work environment, where employees can express ideas, test new approaches, and accelerate work processes. With the freedom and support of leadership, employees are more motivated to create positive change in public services. In the long term, this will strengthen the culture of innovation within the organization and sustainably improve performance.

In the context of public bureaucracy, innovation is not just about technology, but also about how work is done more intelligently and efficiently. Transformational leaders emphasize the importance of adapting work behaviors to the needs of the times and society. Leaders create a shared vision that guides employees beyond simply performing administrative tasks to acting as agents of change. Public innovation driven by transformational leadership not only improves internal processes but also increases public satisfaction with the services provided. Therefore, transformational leadership is a crucial foundation for the emergence of meaningful public innovation.

Innovations born from the influence of transformational leaders are often systemic and sustainable, not just short-term initiatives. Inspirational leaders encourage employees to see problems as opportunities for improvement and develop solutions with broad impact. Leaders also create mechanisms for recognizing and rewarding employees' innovative ideas, which strengthens the spirit of innovation. When these innovations are implemented, the results are reflected in work efficiency, increased customer satisfaction, and the achievement of organizational performance targets.

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Thus, public innovation serves as a strategic mediator between leadership style and employee performance outcomes.

Good employee performance is not only measured by individual work results, but also by their contribution to achieving organizational goals. Transformational leaders encourage synergy between teams through collective innovation that prioritizes cross-unit collaboration. Public innovation resulting from this collective approach can address complex challenges in the public service sector. Employees involved in this type of innovation demonstrate increased engagement, a sense of belonging, and commitment to the organization. This demonstrates that transformational leadership, which creates an innovative climate, plays a significant role in developing high-performing employees. According to Mulgan & Albury (2003), "public innovation is about finding new ways to deliver better services, deliver more effective policies, and enhance citizen engagement in the processes of governance." This view emphasizes the importance of public innovation as a means to create better services and increase citizen engagement. Transformational leaders are highly relevant because they are able to foster a spirit of change and active participation among employees. When public innovation is running optimally, employees become more responsive to community needs. This demonstrates that the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance is strengthened by the role of innovation in public service.

The use of information technology in public innovation, spearheaded by transformational leaders, also contributes to employee work efficiency. Utami (2023) state that public innovation in Indonesia is directed at improving the quality of public services through information technology. Transformational leaders support the use of technology as a strategic tool to accelerate processes, increase accuracy, and expand service reach. In this context, employees find it easier to work and are encouraged to continuously hone their competencies. Improved performance also demonstrates that targeted public innovation positively contributes to employee performance. Transformational leadership facilitates a work culture open to change, a crucial prerequisite for successful public innovation. With open dialogue, constructive feedback, and ongoing support from superiors, employees feel safe and confident in trying new approaches. Innovations created in this environment are typically more structured, data-driven, and targeted at tangible service improvements. When innovations are successfully implemented, this provides additional motivation for employees to perform better.

Transformational leadership also teaches the importance of long-term vision in innovation. Employees are encouraged to think not only about today's results but also about the long-term impact on the organization and society. In this

way, innovation is not reactive but becomes part of the organization's ongoing strategy. Employees working within this system will develop a strong sense of responsibility and a focus on sustainable results. This is the optimal performance achieved through inspirational leadership and planned public innovation.

Organizational culture influences employee performance through public innovation. This means that the values, norms, and habits embedded within an organization can create an environment that encourages innovation, which in turn improves employee performance. An organizational culture that supports openness, collaboration, and learning will encourage employees to develop new ways of performing their duties. Public innovation that grows from this culture not only improves efficiency but also the quality of service to the public. When an organizational culture encourages experimentation and tolerance for failure, employees will be more willing to try new approaches. This creates a synergy between work culture and innovation, resulting in more optimal work results.

A strong organizational culture is the foundation for creating change through continuous innovation. When organizational values encourage adaptation to change and creative problem-solving, employees are motivated to continuously improve their performance. Public innovation, driven by this organizational culture, reflects a willingness to think outside the box in providing public services. As a result, employees can work more effectively and efficiently in achieving organizational goals. Thus, public innovation serves as a crucial bridge connecting organizational culture with employee performance.

Organizations that foster a collaborative culture are more likely to foster innovation because interactions between employees can generate new, creative ideas. Employees feel more involved and have an active role in the policy and work program development process. This culture provides space for each individual to voice their ideas and collectively improve work processes. The public innovations that emerge from this process will create a more responsive work mechanism that aligns with community needs.

According to Schraeder et al. (2005), organizational culture is holistic, soft, difficult to change, historically based, and socially constructed. This suggests that the influence of organizational culture is not instantaneous, but requires time and continuity to shape employee mindsets and behaviors. When this culture is directed toward supporting innovation, organizational habits that are adaptive to change are formed. Employees thrive in a work environment that encourages continuous learning and performance improvement. Therefore, public innovation becomes a strategic channel for transmitting organizational cultural values toward quality performance output.

Research by Al Haderi (2014) found that government organizations with strong organizational culture

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demonstrated a high level of responsiveness to customer needs. This demonstrates that an adaptive organizational culture open to input can foster innovation relevant to public demands. Employees within the organization will have a greater awareness of the importance of performance in public services. Public innovation provides a means to address these needs quickly and accurately. As a result, employee performance improves not only in terms of quantity but also in terms of the quality of service provided.

Public innovations generated from organizational cultural values also accelerate bureaucratic processes, often considered slow and rigid. Employees working in a culture that encourages efficiency will use technology, new work methods, or digital service systems to expedite service delivery. This innovation helps reduce administrative workloads and increase employee productivity. In the long term, an innovation-friendly organizational culture will create a more dynamic work cycle and positively impact performance. Employees not only complete tasks but also contribute to organizational transformation.

An organizational culture that provides space for regular dialogue, reflection, and evaluation will enrich the public innovation process. Through this mechanism, employees can learn from experiences, address weaknesses, and improve service strategies. This strengthens the organization's capacity for continuous innovation. Thus, an open and reflective organizational culture is a key driving force for successful innovation and improved performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions drawn from this study are: Transformational leadership and organizational culture influence employee performance. Leaders who are able to inspire, motivate, and create a positive work environment, as well as an organizational culture that supports collaborative, innovative, and accountable values, have been shown to improve employee performance.

Transformational leadership and organizational culture influence public innovation. Visionary leadership and an organizational culture open to change can foster public innovation, whether in the form of new ideas, work methods, or public services that are more responsive to community needs.

Public innovation impacts employee performance. Innovations developed within public organizations can accelerate work processes and increase efficiency, but they also provide room for employee creativity and improve service quality, thus directly impacting employee performance.

Transformational leadership and organizational culture play a crucial role in improving employee performance, but their influence becomes even more effective when mediated by public innovation. Visionary and inspiring leaders can create a spirit of renewal in the workplace, while an open and

adaptive organizational culture provides a conducive space for the growth of innovative ideas. Public innovation then plays a key role in transforming work systems, accelerating services, and increasing bureaucratic efficiency. In the Pamekasan Regency Government, the synergy between transformational leadership, a positive organizational culture, and public innovation is a key strategy in developing high-performing, professional employees who are responsive to community needs.

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